

Original article

Challenges of managing retinoblastoma in a resource-constrained setting: a 4.5-year retrospective review from Northeastern Nigeria

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Abstract

Background: Retinoblastoma is the leading intraocular cancer in children, with treatment outcomes significantly poorer in low-resource settings such as Nigeria. This study, conducted at the Federal University of Health Sciences Teaching Hospital, Azare, reviewed the clinical profiles and treatment outcomes of 28 patients diagnosed with retinoblastoma from January 2020 to June 2024. **Materials and Methods:** It is a hospital-based retrospective study. Ethical approval was secured, and data collected included demographics, symptoms, tumour stage, treatment modalities, and follow-up results. **Results:** The cohort of patients, aged 0-60 months, had a mean presentation age of 23.8 months, with a male-to-female ratio of 1.3:1. The most common symptom was proptosis, noted in 67.9% of cases, and 25% presented with bilateral disease. The majority, 50%, were classified as Group D in the International Intraocular Retinoblastoma Classification. Alarming, treatment abandonment was high, with 75% of patients dropping out after initial presentations. Only 25% proceeded to aggressive treatments like enucleation or modified exenteration. **Conclusion:** The study highlights critical challenges such as late presentation and high rates of treatment abandonment, paralleling trends in Nigeria and across Africa. To address these issues, increased community awareness, better referral systems, and enhanced psychosocial support are urgently needed to improve management and outcomes for retinoblastoma in these settings.

Keywords: Childhood cancer, Enucleation, Late presentation, Resource-limited setting, Retinoblastoma, Treatment abandonment

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Introduction

Retinoblastoma is the most common primary intraocular malignancy of childhood, accounting for approximately 3% of all childhood cancers.¹ It results from biallelic inactivation of the *RB1* tumour suppressor gene located on chromosome 13q14, with both heritable (40%) and non-heritable (60%) forms recognised.² If untreated, retinoblastoma is uniformly fatal; however, with early diagnosis and appropriate multimodal therapy, survival rates exceed 95% in high-income countries.³

The global burden of retinoblastoma is disproportionately borne by low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), where over 80% of the world's children live and where healthcare resources are severely constrained.⁴ A recent systematic review of orbito-ocular tumours in Nigeria confirmed that retinoblastoma is the most common malignant tumour in children, with proptosis being the most frequent presenting symptom.⁵ Across the African continent, outcomes remain poor—a large prospective study involving 958 patients from 41 African countries reported a 1-year survival rate of only 78.2% and a 3-year survival rate of 66.2%, with advanced clinical stage strongly predicting mortality.^{6,7}

Nigeria, as Africa's most populous nation, bears a substantial burden of childhood cancer. A 10-year review from Calabar, Southern Nigeria, documented an increasing incidence of retinoblastoma, with the age-standardised incidence rate rising from 0.16 to 0.27 per 100,000 children over the study period.⁸ Alarming, that same study found that 66.4% of children presented with late-stage disease, 42.8% abandoned treatment, and the crude mortality rate for retinoblastoma increased tenfold over the decade.⁸ Similarly, another study from Calabar identified delayed presentation, low socioeconomic status, and incomplete chemotherapy as significant predictors of mortality.⁹

Northeastern Nigeria faces unique challenges that compound these already difficult circumstances. The region has experienced prolonged insurgency, displacement of populations, and destruction of health infrastructure, further limiting access to cancer care. Climate-related disasters, such as flooding, have also been shown to disrupt childhood oncology services in Nigeria, with patients unable to access facilities due to road damage and telecommunications network failures.¹⁰

This study, conducted at the Federal University of Health Sciences Teaching Hospital, Azare, located in Bauchi State, Northeastern Nigeria, aimed to document the clinical profile, treatment outcomes, and specific challenges encountered in managing retinoblastoma in this resource-constrained setting. By highlighting these realities, we hope to inform strategies for improving early detection, treatment adherence, and ultimately survival for children with this potentially curable cancer.

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Setting

This was a hospital-based retrospective study conducted in the Ophthalmology and Paediatrics Departments of the Federal University of Health Sciences Teaching Hospital, Azare, a tertiary health facility in Bauchi State, North-Eastern Nigeria. The centre serves as a referral hub for retinoblastoma cases from across the northeastern region, including Bauchi, Gombe, Yobe, and parts of Borno and Adamawa states.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the Health Research Ethics Committee of Federal University of Health Sciences Teaching Hospital, Azare. The study adhered to the tenets of the Declaration of Helsinki. Given the retrospective nature of the study, the ethics committee waived the requirement for individual patient consent, but all patient data were anonymised before analysis.

Study Period and Population

All patients diagnosed with retinoblastoma between January 2020 and June 2024 (a 4.5-year period) were included in the review. Diagnosis was based on clinical examination findings (leukocoria, strabismus, proptosis) and imaging (orbital ultrasound and/or computed tomography, where available). Histopathological confirmation was obtained for patients who underwent enucleation.

Data Collection

Data were extracted from case files using a standardised proforma. Information collected included:

- **Demographic characteristics:** Age at presentation, sex, address/geographic origin
- **Clinical presentation:** Presenting complaints, duration of symptoms before presentation, laterality (unilateral vs. bilateral)
- **Tumour staging:** Using the International Intraocular Retinoblastoma Classification (IIRC): Groups A through E
- **Treatment:** Chemotherapy (agents, cycles completed), surgery (enucleation, exenteration), radiotherapy, refusal/abandonment of treatment
- **Outcomes:** Completion of treatment, default/loss to follow-up, referral elsewhere, death (where documented)

Treatment abandonment was defined as failure to return for scheduled treatment for ≥ 4 weeks after the planned date, consistent with definitions used in similar studies.⁸

Data Analysis

Data were entered into Microsoft Excel and analysed using SPSS version 25 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). Descriptive statistics were computed, including means, standard deviations, and proportions. Given the small sample size and high default rate, inferential statistical analysis was limited.

Results

A total of 28 patients with retinoblastoma were diagnosed and managed during the 4.5-year study period. These 28 patients accounted for 35 affected eyes (7 patients had bilateral disease). The age range at presentation was 0–60 months, with a mean age of 23.8 ± 7.8 months. There were 16 males (57.1%) and 12 females (42.9%), giving a male-to-female ratio of 1.3:1. Table 1 summarises the demographic characteristics of the study population.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Retinoblastoma Patients (N=28)

Characteristic	Freq (n)	Per cent (%)
Age group (months)		
0–12	6	21.4
13–24	12	42.9
25–36	7	25.0
37–60	3	10.7
Sex		
Male	16	57.1
Female	12	42.9
Laterality		
Unilateral	21	75.0
Bilateral	7	25.0

Clinical Presentation

The duration of symptoms before presentation at our facility ranged from 8 months to 2 years, indicating severe delays in accessing care. Proptosis (eye protrusion) was the most common presenting complaint, observed in 19 patients (67.9%). Other

presenting features included Leukocoria (white pupil) (8 patients, 28.6%), strabismus (4 patients, 14.3%), and orbital cellulitis-like presentation with redness and swelling (3 patients, 10.7%). Many patients presented with multiple symptoms. Table 2 summarises the presenting complaints.

Table 2: Presenting Complaints (N=28; multiple complaints possible)

Presenting Complaint	Freq (n)	Percent (%)
Proptosis (eye protrusion)	19	67.9
Leukocoria (white pupil)	8	28.6
Strabismus (squint)	4	14.3
Redness/swelling (orbital cellulitis-like)	3	10.7
Poor vision/vision loss	3	10.7

Tumour Stage at Presentation

Using the International Intraocular Retinoblastoma Classification (IIRC), Group D was the most common stage at presentation, documented in 14 patients (50.0%). Group E disease (advanced, with high-risk features) was present in 8 patients (28.6%). Only 6 patients (21.4%) presented with earlier-stage disease (Groups B and C). No patient presented with Group A disease during the study period.

Table 3 shows the distribution of tumour stages.

Table 3: Intraocular Tumour Stage at Presentation (IIRC Classification) (N=28)

Tumour Stage	Freq (n)	Percent (%)
Group A	0	0.0
Group B	2	7.1
Group C	4	14.3
Group D	14	50.0
Group E	8	28.6

Treatment and Outcomes

Treatment outcomes were profoundly affected by high rates of treatment abandonment. The chemotherapy regimen used in all patients was Vincristine, Etoposide and Carboplatin. Of the 28 patients:

- **21 patients (75.0%)** defaulted from treatment after the first or second hospital visit. These patients either did not return for planned chemotherapy or declined surgical intervention after initial counselling.
- **Only 7 patients (25.0%)** consented to and underwent surgical intervention. Among these:
 - 5 patients underwent enucleation (for Group E disease at presentation)
 - 2 patients underwent modified exenteration (for orbital disease after chemoreduction was attempted but defaulted)

Of the 7 patients with bilateral disease, none received adequate bilateral treatment. All either defaulted or had only the worst eye addressed surgically before loss to follow-up.

Table 4 summarises treatment outcomes.

Table 4: Treatment and Outcomes (N=28)

Outcome	Freq (n)	Percent (%)
Defaulted/abandoned treatment	21	75.0
Consented to surgery	7	25.0
- Enucleation performed	5	17.9
- Modified exenteration performed	2	7.1
Completed planned treatment	0	0.0
Referred to a higher centre (but defaulted)	4	14.3

None of the 28 patients completed the full planned course of treatment (chemotherapy, surgery, and follow-up) at our centre. Four patients were referred to larger oncology centres at Kano, northwestern Nigeria, as free chemotherapy was provided through Christophel Blind Mission, but

all were lost to follow-up and could not be traced for outcome assessment. The National Health Insurance Authority (NHIA) benefits package did not cover retinoblastoma care. Psychosocial support is limited for patients in our centre. Mortality data were incomplete due to the high default rate, but at least 3 patients were known to have died from progressive disease based on family reports.

Discussion

This study from Northeastern Nigeria highlights the profound challenges facing retinoblastoma management in resource-constrained settings. The mean age at presentation of 23.8 months in our series is similar to that reported in the African Retinoblastoma Study (median 24 months)⁶ and the Calabar series (median 24 months).⁹ However, the duration of symptoms before presentation – ranging from 8 months to 2 years – indicates that many children had visible signs of disease for months or even years before accessing care. In Ibadan, Fasina¹¹ documented similar patterns of late presentation. Templeton's¹² early work in Uganda established the foundational epidemiology of eye tumours in Africa, against which contemporary studies continue to show persistently delayed presentation. This delay occurs at multiple levels: caregiver delay in recognising the significance of symptoms, delay in seeking care from primary health centres, and delay in referral to tertiary centres capable of diagnosis and treatment. Proptosis was the most common presenting sign in our series (67.9%), which is consistent with findings of the systematic review by Nathaniel et al.⁵ which identified proptosis as the most frequent symptom in Nigerian orbito-ocular tumours overall. This concordance is likely due to the specific focus on retinoblastoma in our study, compared with all orbito-ocular tumours in the review. This contrasts with findings from Ghana, where Essuman et al.¹³ reported leukocoria as the predominant presenting feature. In many communities in Northern Nigeria, white pupillary reflex may be misinterpreted as a normal variant or attributed to spiritual causes, leading to delayed care-seeking, similar to cultural barriers documented in other African settings.¹³ The predominance of advanced disease at presentation in our study (50% Group D, 28.6% Group E) directly reflects these delays. This finding aligns closely with the Calabar 10-year review by Nlemadim et al.⁸ which reported 66.4% late-stage presentation, and the African continent study by Nishath et al.⁶ where the majority of patients presented with advanced disease. Group D and E

tumours carry high risks of metastasis and death, and they almost invariably require enucleation rather than globe-sparing therapies.¹⁴ The absence of any Group A patients in our series underscores that early-stage, treatable retinoblastoma is simply not being detected in the community.

The most striking finding of this study is the 75% treatment abandonment rate, one of the highest reported in the literature. This rate substantially exceeds the 42.8% abandonment rate reported from Calabar by Nlemadim et al.⁸ for all childhood cancers, and is considerably higher than rates documented in other Nigerian studies.^{9,14} Nkanga et al.⁹ identified incomplete chemotherapy (hazard ratio 5.61) and relapse (hazard ratio 5.98) as significant predictors of mortality in their Calabar cohort, highlighting the consequences of treatment interruption. The higher abandonment rate in our Northeastern Nigeria setting likely reflects the compounded effects of extreme poverty, ongoing insurgency, and destruction of health infrastructure in the region, as documented by the United Nations humanitarian reports.¹⁴

Treatment abandonment in retinoblastoma is multifactorial. Financial barriers are paramount, as the cost of cancer treatment in Nigeria is overwhelmingly borne out-of-pocket, with limited health insurance coverage. Mostert et al.¹⁵ in Kenya similarly identified financial constraints and weak social networks as key contributors to treatment abandonment. Distance and transportation pose particular challenges in Northeastern Nigeria, where families from Yobe, Gombe, or Borno states face journeys of 200-500 km through areas with poor road networks and active security threats. Cultural beliefs and misconceptions about surgery, particularly enucleation, which may be perceived as mutilation, further compound the problem. Unlike in high-income countries, where multidisciplinary teams include psychosocial support, such services are virtually non-existent in our setting. Additionally, the ongoing insurgency in Northeastern Nigeria has displaced millions and disrupted health services,¹⁶ preventing even willing families from accessing care.

The consequences of treatment abandonment are devastating. Children with untreated retinoblastoma develop progressive disease with orbital extension, metastasis (most commonly to the brain and bone), and death. In the African Retinoblastoma Study, advanced clinical stage (cT4) was associated with a 6.3-fold increased risk of death.⁶ Our 75% abandonment rate is higher than most published series, likely reflecting the extreme circumstances of Northeastern Nigeria, where

many children with retinoblastoma never reach tertiary care, dying undiagnosed in the community.¹⁷ West et al.¹⁰ have also documented how climate-related disasters such as flooding disrupt childhood oncology services in Nigeria, further compounding these challenges.

Comparison with other Nigerian regional studies reveals important geographical variations. The systematic review by Nathaniel et al.⁵ confirmed that retinoblastoma is the most common childhood orbital-ocular tumour nationally. Uche et al.¹⁸ in Enugu reported clinico profiles consistent with our findings, but our study did not report pathological findings, while Mohammed et al.¹⁹ in Zaria (Northern Nigeria) documented orbito-ocular tumour patterns comparable to our series.

The survival outcomes in our series could not be accurately calculated due to the high default rate, but the known mortality of at least 3 patients (10.7%) likely represents significant under-ascertainment. This compares poorly with the African Retinoblastoma Study by Nishath et al.⁶ which reported 78.2% 1-year survival and 66.2% 3-year survival across 41 African countries. Our findings are more consistent with the Cameroon experience reported by Kruger et al.¹⁷ where even with staged treatment protocols per SIOP-PODC guidelines, 2-year overall survival was only 50%. The authors demonstrated that structured protocols can improve outcomes even in low-income settings, achieving 68.8% survival for limited disease,¹⁷ suggesting a potential pathway for improvement in our context.²⁰ The Global Retinoblastoma Study Group's⁷ prospective analysis of 4064 patients from 149 countries confirmed that low-income settings consistently have poorer outcomes, with our study representing an extreme within that spectrum.

Limitations

This study has some limitations that should be considered when interpreting the findings:

1. **Retrospective design:** The study's retrospective nature and reliance on medical records meant that some data (e.g., exact dates, detailed socioeconomic information, long-term survival) were incomplete.
2. **High default rate:** The 75% treatment abandonment rate precluded accurate assessment of treatment response and survival outcomes.
3. **Limited histopathological confirmation:** Histopathological confirmation was available only for the few patients who underwent surgery; other

diagnoses were based on clinical and imaging findings.

4. **Single-centre design:** The single-centre design limits generalisability, though our findings are consistent with other Nigerian reports from Calabar,^{8,9} Ibadan,¹⁷ Enugu,¹⁸ and Zaria.¹⁹
5. **Incomplete mortality data:** Due to the high loss to follow-up, mortality data were incomplete, with only 3 deaths documented, which likely represents significant under-reporting.
6. **Study period confounders:** The study period (2020-2024) coincided with the COVID-19 pandemic and ongoing insurgency in Northeastern Nigeria, which may have exacerbated treatment abandonment and limited access to care.

Conclusion

This study highlights the severe challenges in managing retinoblastoma in Northeastern Nigeria, characterised by late diagnoses, prolonged symptom duration, and a 75% treatment abandonment rate. No patients completed their treatment protocols, probably due to cultural and financial barriers obstructing care-seeking efforts. Urgent, multi-level interventions are necessary, including community health education, training for healthcare workers, strengthening diagnostic capabilities, policy inclusions for childhood cancer care, and psychosocial support for families. Immediate actions by various stakeholders are critical to improving the chances of survival for these children.

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Conflict of Interest Statement

The authors declare no conflicts of interest relevant to this manuscript.

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Authors' Contributions

- **MDA:** Conceptualisation, Clinical management, study design, data collection, final approval

- **YMO:** Clinical management, Data collection, manuscript review, final approval
- **IBA:** Data collection, study design, manuscript drafting, final approval
- **USE:** Histopathological analysis, manuscript review, final approval
- **MAB:** Data collection, manuscript review, final approval

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